

Scalable AI-Driven Video Generation for Waste Picker Education: A Localized Approach Using Open-Source Models

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15874357>

Abstract

This paper presents the development of an AI-driven application designed to scale the production of educational videos for waste pickers within the Educado project, part of the Egalitarian program. The application integrates three open-source AI models, Flux AI for persona generation, Coqui AI for speech synthesis, and SadTalker for realistic lip-sync, allowing for the creation of engaging, locally produced educational content without reliance on external connections. Designed to run on relatively modest hardware (16-core CPU, 32GB RAM at 7400Mt/s, and 6GB dedicated VRAM), this solution ensures accessibility in resource-constrained environments. The goal is to address the challenge of efficiently generating high-quality educational materials that can be easily adapted to the specific needs of waste pickers, a crucial yet often overlooked workforce in waste management. The system enables the automatic creation of virtual educators, delivering spoken lessons with synchronized lip movements, simulating a real instructor. A key limitation is the management of multiple personas within a single video, which is currently mitigated by generating a character with a green screen background and layering them in post-production. The proposed framework demonstrates how open-source AI tools can enhance educational access for underserved communities while maintaining operational independence from cloud-based services. This paper details the implementation of the application, its challenges, and its potential for scalability in the production of educational content. Future work will focus on improving multi-persona integration, integrating another AI assistant that is tailored to specific areas of knowledge to aid researchers and also generating scripts using trusted references, and expanding the applicability of the system to broader educational contexts.

Keywords: AI-generated; Educational; Lip-sync; Open-source; Innovation.

1 Introduction

As part of the development of the EDUCADO project within the ERASMUS+ EGALITARIAN program, the primary goal is to produce educational content focused on financial literacy and occupational health and safety for solid waste pickers in Brazil. One of the main challenges encountered during implementation was the creation of videos that could effectively and efficiently convey knowledge to audiences with diverse educational backgrounds.

Traditional audiovisual content production requires a complex process, including studio rental, professional equipment, and detailed post-production editing. This approach is often costly, time-consuming, and limits scalability. To overcome these barriers, the project explored methodologies to automate and optimize video creation while preserving instructional quality and learner engagement.

This work adopts a design-based case study approach, integrating iterative field testing with solid waste picker cooperatives. This method allows for continual refinement of tools based on real-world feedback and needs, aligning well with engineering education principles of problem-solving, stakeholder engagement, and user-centered design (Barab & Squire, 2004).

In response to these challenges, the project adopted vlog-style videos—a format known for its informal, dynamic, and relatable presentation style. Vlogs facilitate more personal communication, improving audience connection and motivation, particularly in adult education contexts (Green et al., 2020). Research shows that

video content delivered through accessible, informal formats can significantly enhance learning outcomes and increase digital participation in marginalized communities (Yousef et al., 2014).

Beyond producing content for waste pickers, the project also supports the creation of digital personas representing workers and mobilizers—community members responsible for educating households on waste separation. These personas contribute to social legitimacy and extend the reach of awareness campaigns by providing culturally relevant and representative messaging. This approach leverages principles of participatory design and aligns with literature on the effectiveness of contextualized educational media (Clark & Mayer, 2023; Kali et al., 2018).

By combining innovative media formats with open-source AI tools, the EDUCADO project fosters a scalable and inclusive digital learning ecosystem. Educational videos can be distributed through social media and local networks, creating a decentralized, low-cost model of community-centered knowledge dissemination. This design-based innovation serves not only pedagogical objectives but also broader goals of digital equity and social inclusion.

2 Methodology

This study follows a design-based research (DBR) approach (Barab & Squire, 2004; McKenney & Reeves, 2012), which combines iterative development with real-world testing to refine educational tools through continuous feedback. The methodology integrates principles from engineering design, educational psychology, and open-source software development to build a system that is both scalable and socially impactful.

The software was developed in stages, beginning with the identification of user requirements and progressing through iterative cycles of design, testing, and optimization with cooperative waste picker communities in Brazil. The process emphasized contextual adaptation, learner inclusiveness, and low-barrier deployment.

To ensure alignment with pedagogical, technical, and accessibility goals, a set of development principles was established.

2.1 Design Guidelines and Pedagogical Parameters

To ensure that the software aligned with both its pedagogical goals and technical feasibility in low-resource environments, a set of engineering design parameters was established. These guidelines reflect the principles of user-centered design and iterative refinement common in engineering and software development (Sommerville, 2015; McKenney & Reeves, 2012), and they were shaped by ongoing collaboration with the target audience through the EDUCADO fieldwork.

- **Ease of Use:**
 - The software was designed to be intuitive for users with limited digital literacy. Interface decisions were informed by usability engineering principles (Nielsen, 1994) and validated through user testing in waste picker cooperatives. Clear visual steps and modular automation allow users to create video content without prior technical training.
- **Fidelity in Representation:**
 - Visual and instructional consistency was prioritized to enhance trust and recognition. A standardized set of colors, fonts, and avatars was used to reinforce brand identity and maintain clarity across multiple educational topics. This aligns with research showing that consistent design improves learner focus and message credibility (Clark & Mayer, 2023; Holden & Butler, 2003).
- **Accessibility through Open-Source Tools:**
 - The system uses only free and open-source models, ensuring legal freedom for adaptation and reducing barriers to use in community-led initiatives. This aligns with long-standing open

software values around educational freedom (Stallman, 2002) and supports knowledge democratization in engineering education.

- Low Operational Cost:
 - By enabling offline execution on mid-tier hardware, the platform eliminates dependence on cloud services, which are often unaffordable or unavailable in marginalized communities. The model operates with only a 16-core CPU, 32GB RAM, and a 6GB GPU—demonstrating how resource efficiency is a key enabler of digital inclusion (Abadi et al., 2016).
- Realism in Presentation:
 - The integration of AI-powered lip-sync (SadTalker) and expressive avatars improves the clarity and perceived authenticity of instructional content. Research on multimedia learning confirms that realistic visual and auditory synchrony enhances understanding and engagement (Mayer, 2005; Clark & Mayer, 2023).

These development principles not only guided the technical architecture of the EDUCADO application but also serve as a pedagogical framework for engineering students and educators interested in building equitable digital solutions. The design process offers a replicable model for socially relevant educational innovation, emphasizing simplicity, openness, and contextual fidelity.

2.2 Software Architecture and Module Breakdown

The software was structured around a modular architecture to enable flexible development, efficient resource use, and user-oriented interaction. This modularization also allowed iterative testing and refinement in real learning environments, consistent with the principles of design-based research (Barab & Squire, 2004).

Each module performs a specific function in the pipeline of video lesson generation, contributing to the system's overarching educational goals: accessibility, scalability, and pedagogical effectiveness.

2.2.1 Module 1 - Data Input and Content Configuration

The user begins by inputting the lesson script and selecting a character for the video. Options include choosing a pre-designed avatar or generating a new one using pre-set parameters. This module emphasizes ease of use and was designed with usability heuristics in mind (Nielsen, 1994). Field testing showed that users with minimal technical background could successfully complete this step, validating the system's design for low-barrier use in community settings.

2.2.2 Module 2 - Image Generation with AI

The image generation module uses Flux AI to produce character images aligned with predefined visual guidelines. The AI generates images using a 9:16 format optimized for mobile display, with parameters for lighting, background, and expression embedded in the prompt.

Users can iterate through outputs until a suitable image is selected, ensuring personalization and cultural relevance. These visual outputs contribute to learner engagement and identification, both essential for effective educational media (Clark & Mayer, 2023). The module balances visual quality with processing efficiency, running locally even on mid-range hardware (Abadi et al., 2016).

2.2.3 Module 3 - Text-to-Speech (TTS) and Voice Cloning

This module converts the lesson script into speech using the Coqui AI model. While initial attempts at custom training required significant resources, the final implementation uses pre-trained models with small-scale fine-tuning to retain realism and clarity. The voice output is synchronized with the selected persona and supports regional linguistic features for relevance.

According to principles of multimedia learning (Mayer, 2005), realistic, well-paced narration significantly improves knowledge retention. This module's success was validated through field sessions where waste pickers showed increased attention and comprehension when hearing familiar speech patterns.

2.2.4 Module 4 - Lip Synchronization and Animation

To animate the avatar with realistic facial expressions and lip movements, the system employs SadTalker. This model enables synchronized animation based on the generated speech and static image. Beyond syncing lip movement, it incorporates subtle expressions and eye/head movements that enhance the illusion of a human presenter.

Feedback from pilot deployments highlighted that learners perceived these avatars as more "relatable" and "trustworthy" than traditional animated or slide-based videos. This aligns with findings that personalized, expressive content improves learner engagement in informal education (Green et al., 2020; Clark & Mayer, 2023).

2.2.5 Integration and Workflow Efficiency

Each module operates in a virtual environment to isolate dependencies and prevent compatibility issues, following best practices in software engineering (Sommerville, 2015). The pipeline supports CLI (command-line interface) execution to optimize performance and reduce overhead, critical in environments with limited digital infrastructure.

The modular design also enables future extensibility, such as multi-avatar scenarios or integration with AI script assistants. Throughout development, field testing in waste picker cooperatives provided crucial feedback for improving usability and refining system outputs, an essential element of the design-based research cycle (McKenney & Reeves, 2012).

3 Implementation and Field Evaluation

The development of said application followed a structured and iterative approach to optimize execution time and resource utilization. To ensure efficiency and modularity, each component was developed independently while maintaining seamless integration in the final video generation workflow. The primary development steps were as follows:

- Virtual environment setup:
 - Each AI model used in the application required specific software dependencies and libraries, making it unfeasible to run them all in a single environment without conflicts. To address this, isolated virtual environments were created for each model, ensuring compatibility with specific Python versions and dependencies. This setup was managed using Conda and Python's native virtual environments, allowing independent execution of each module while avoiding package conflicts. Research on software engineering best practices highlights that isolating dependencies improves system stability and prevents compatibility issues in AI-driven applications (Abadi et al., 2016).
- Validation of required libraries:
 - The AI models used in the software relied on several libraries for proper functioning. Key dependencies such as PyTorch, TensorFlow, and Librosa required specific versions to ensure compatibility with the selected models. Each environment was configured to include only the strictly necessary libraries, reducing unnecessary memory consumption and processing overhead. This approach optimizes performance and minimizes the risk of unexpected failures during execution (Abadi et al., 2016).
- Validation of native execution:

- A core requirement of the project was ensuring that all models could run locally without relying on external servers or cloud-based APIs. This decision was essential to maintain data privacy, avoid recurring operational costs, and increase accessibility in low-connectivity environments. However, some models were initially developed for Linux environments, posing a challenge since the application needed to run on Windows. To overcome this, compatibility layers such as Windows Subsystem for Linux (WSL) and MinGW were tested, enabling the execution of Linux-based libraries within the Windows environment. Studies confirm that local execution of AI models significantly enhances security and reduces long-term maintenance costs (Stallman, 2002).

After validating these three foundational aspects, each software module was developed independently, leading to specialized processes for image generation, text-to-speech conversion, video synthesis, and final application execution.

3.1 Image generation

The first module developed was the image generation system, powered by Flux AI, an open-source model selected for its resource efficiency and ability to generate expressive avatars. The model was fine-tuned to prioritize waist-up, well-lit compositions in a 9:16 aspect ratio, optimizing output for mobile devices—the primary platform used by waste pickers and mobilizers.

A user feedback loop was implemented, allowing iteration on generated images. For example, keywords like “neutral background” or “smiling” produced more consistent results, reducing user frustration. This iterative improvement supported accessibility for non-technical users while enabling identity representation through culturally appropriate visual cues.

On average, each image required 6–10 minutes of processing using a 16-core CPU and 6GB GPU. The trade-off between rendering quality and processing speed was continuously evaluated, favoring usability in constrained environments.

3.2 Text-to-speech conversion

The second module performs text-to-speech (TTS) conversion using the Coqui AI voice cloning framework. After initial experiments with large custom voice datasets proved hardware-intensive, the team opted for a pre-trained model with fine-tuning based on 3 hours of targeted recordings.

This compromise allowed for natural-sounding, regionally appropriate voices to be deployed locally. A two-minute voice file could be generated in under 40 seconds. Based on multimedia learning principles (Mayer, 2005), the use of conversational tone and clearly paced narration improved message retention and user engagement.

Field feedback led to adjustments in voice pitch and emphasis to match local idioms and reduce cognitive load.

3.3 Video generation

The third module combines voice and avatar image using SadTalker, an AI model designed to synchronize lip movement and generate realistic facial expressions. This module not only aligns speech and visual output but also introduces subtle head and eye movements for added realism.

Processing time for a 1–2 minute video ranged between 8–14 minutes, depending on complexity. The choice of this model was based on its compatibility with still images and the quality of expressiveness—both key to maintaining attention in video-based learning.

This approach significantly outperformed traditional slide narration, especially in community feedback, where users described the experience as “watching a person explain,” instead of “just hearing a machine.”

3.4 Standalone executable application

To ensure usability in real-world settings—including cooperatives and educational centers without high-performance computing resources—the entire platform was compiled into a lightweight standalone executable. This executable integrates all modules (image generation, voice synthesis, and animation) into a streamlined workflow, eliminating the need for installation of external dependencies.

Instead of building a full graphical user interface (GUI), the project opted for a command-line interface (CLI), for three primary reasons:

- Reduced resource consumption: GUI frameworks typically introduce additional memory and processing overhead, which could hinder performance on mid-range consumer hardware.
- Simplified distribution and portability: A CLI application can be deployed easily on devices with limited storage or operating system customizations, such as recycled desktops common in community centers.
- Transparency and replicability: For engineering and technical education contexts, CLI-based tools expose the execution logic more clearly, helping learners understand model orchestration and system flow—key learning goals in AI and software development curricula.

To manage the complexity of AI dependencies (e.g., PyTorch, TensorFlow, Librosa), each module was isolated in its own virtual environment using Conda and Python's native venv system. This approach follows best practices in modular software engineering (Sommerville, 2015), reducing library conflicts and improving the system's maintainability.

During field deployment, CLI commands were simplified with predefined templates and example scripts, enabling even users with minimal digital literacy to generate full video lessons. In a pilot workshop, a group of local mobilizers with no prior experience in Python or CLI environments were able to complete the video generation pipeline independently after a brief 15-minute orientation.

This lightweight, CLI-based distribution model reinforces the project's commitment to inclusive, low-barrier educational technology, and provides a foundation for future integration into broader digital literacy and engineering training programs.

3.5 Program execution

The full execution pipeline follows a linear, modular structure, visualized in the flowchart presented in Figure 1. Users begin with script and character selection, followed by sequential processing through image generation, voice synthesis, animation, and video export.

This structured pipeline facilitates transparency in system behavior—an important aspect in interpretable AI systems (Doshi-Velez & Kim, 2017). Furthermore, it enables localized debugging, modular testing, and customization by advanced users, including university students and faculty exploring open-source AI for educational development.

The visual model was designed not only as technical documentation, but also as a learning tool for engineering education, illustrating how AI components can be orchestrated to solve real-world instructional challenges.

Figure 1. Image of the application Flowchart

3.6 Practical results

As part of the development cycle, the software was tested during field activities carried out under the EDUCADO project and the Digital Mobilizer initiative. These sessions involved direct engagement with waste picker cooperatives and local mobilization teams in Brazil.

During the demonstrations, participants viewed images generated by the system. The personalized avatars were well received, particularly due to their familiarity and expressiveness. Figures 2 and 3 illustrate examples of the avatars used in these sessions. Participants often remarked that the presenters felt relatable, and the natural tone of the speech enhanced comprehension of topics such as occupational health, financial literacy, and proper waste separation.

Figure 2. Woman generated by the software

Figure 3. Man generated by the software

The presence of culturally relevant visual and linguistic features helped foster a stronger connection between the audience and the content, reinforcing the material's accessibility and impact. These initial field impressions confirmed that even in the absence of formal assessment tools, the system effectively supported its educational objectives.

Insights gathered during these sessions led to adjustments in avatar diversity and refinements in the content scripting process, ensuring the platform remains aligned with the real needs and expectations of its users. This phase of testing reinforced the software's potential as both a scalable content generator and a culturally responsive educational tool for underserved communities.

4 Conclusion

The development of this AI-powered content generation platform represents a meaningful advancement in the creation of inclusive educational resources for underserved communities, particularly waste pickers in Brazil. By integrating open-source AI tools for image generation, speech synthesis, and lip synchronization, the system enables scalable, localized video production that operates independently from cloud infrastructure—thereby addressing key barriers related to cost, connectivity, and technical complexity.

Preliminary field testing conducted through the EDUCADO and Digital Mobilizer initiatives demonstrated positive reception from target users. Participants expressed strong identification with the generated avatars, reporting that the familiar speech patterns and expressive visuals made the content more relatable and easier to follow. One waste picker commented that “the instructor looked like someone from our community,” highlighting the social value of personalization. Based on feedback, improvements were made to avatar diversity, voice clarity, and script simplicity to enhance engagement. From an engineering and higher education perspective, this study offers a practical and socially relevant case for integrating ethical, user-centered AI into curriculum and research. It exemplifies how design-based research can bridge theory and practice by combining iterative prototyping, stakeholder feedback, and technological innovation. The solution aligns with educational goals in engineering disciplines by demonstrating how students and professionals can build systems that are technically robust, ethically grounded, and context-aware.

Future work will focus on expanding the system's capacity to support multi-persona narratives, incorporating an AI assistant to support script generation with trusted references, and exploring broader applications in vocational and adult education. Ultimately, this project contributes to both educational access and engineering practice by demonstrating how localized, open AI tools can be used to create high-impact, community-driven learning solutions.

Acknowledgments

This work was partially developed in the context of project 2023-1-DK01-KA220-HED-00165709, “EGALITARIAN - Education, Digitalisation and Collaboration for Sustainability,” which has been funded with support from the European Commission. This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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